

Continuous Professional Development for Teachers: A Reflection on Teacher Experiences in Selected Schools in Kabwe District, Zambia

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ABSTRACT

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This study sought to explore the experiences of teachers towards Continuous Professional Development (CPD) in Kabwe District. The objectives of the study were to; establish the forms of CPD activities teachers engage in, discuss the perception of teachers on CPD activities and to find out the relevance of CPD activities on teachers' classroom practices. A sample of 15 teachers were purposively drawn from five schools in Kabwe District. A Qualitative approach and descriptive study design were employed for this study. Data were collected through face-face interviews with teachers and direct observation was done during the CPD meetings for teachers. Data collected were analyzed thematically. The major findings of the study were that teachers were not consulted on the CPD agenda, CPD activities were inadequate and fragmented, the duration and timing of CPD activities was inadequate while participants expressed mixed feeling on the accessibility and relevance of CPD activities on classroom practice. The study recommended inter alia that the Ministry of Education (MoE) should strengthen the monitoring and evaluation of CPD activities.

KEYWORDS:

Continuous Professional Development, Classroom practice, CPD activities, teacher engagement

INTRODUCTION

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is a process of on-going learning and development that helps professionals enhance their knowledge, skills and expertise to improve their professional practice. It is about actively seeking new knowledge and skills, often through various learning activities and reflecting on how these experiences impact work. CPD is an on-going process of frequently improving skills and competencies to enhance workplace performance and future career. CPD can be broadly defined as any type of learning you undertake which increases your knowledge, understanding and experiences of a subject area or role (Borko, 2004). CPD is an on-going and planned learning and development process. CPD of teachers is fundamental to the provision of quality teaching and learning in a country's education system. Competencies of teachers in Zambia do not

seem to have improved as envisaged even in the face of some CPD activities in schools (MoE, 2017). A number of initiatives have been introduced by the MoE in Zambia to improve the competencies of teachers in schools across the country. One aspect which seems to have influenced the failure of the CPD programmes for teachers has been the non-involvement of practitioners when programmes are designed. Ono and Ferreira (2010) confirm that where teachers have been excluded in the design of programmes and policies for CPD that are expert-based with the knowledge and experiences of teachers not being considered, teachers just become absorbers of knowledge transmitted to them in a top-down approach presented in a rigid way, without room for context or for teachers to construct knowledge based on their experiences. Therefore, it becomes difficult for them to translate and contextualise the CPD programmes into the classroom, particularly in rural schools with their own characteristics. Designed from a uniform perspective Ono & Ferreira (2010); & Villegas-Remers (2003) argue that any education reform or improvement that fails to consult teachers in their CPD programmes has not been successful. The balance between experts' knowledge and teachers' experiences has to be forged and sacrificing either is detrimental to any form of teacher development. A further

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challenge for teachers is the lack of teaching and learning aids (Kalimaposo & Mulubale, 2015), particularly for those who teach sciences as these require experiments to enhance understanding; but an absence of teaching and learning aids impairs the competencies of teachers (Mubita, Kalimaposo, Sikayomya, Milupi & Haambakoma, 2022). The challenge becomes how and where to access appropriate professional development programmes that will enable them to improve in their teaching. Some researchers have noted that while professional development had been provided it was not always relevant to the realities of the classrooms of teachers.

Fletcher & Zuber-Skerritt (2007) challenges the cascading model of presenting CPD programmes for teachers as it regards them as passive recipients of the designed programmes and consumers of knowledge produced elsewhere. The assumption in this CPD programme's approach is that teachers can change their behaviour and learn to replicate it in their classrooms (Ono & Ferreira, 2010) but this does not always work.

Another challenge to the implementation of the CPD programmes has been a lack of leadership to ensure that they are relevant at school level. Phiri, et al (2024) found that teachers had observed a lack of opportunities for improvement on the basis of Integrated Quality Management Systems (IQMS) professional development needs. Administrators were rarely prepared to offer useful advice or provide an opportunity for learning. The study further revealed that the leadership did not create a space in which discussions on a one-to-one basis would take place. Teachers did not have a chance to sit down with their Development Support Groups or Staff Development Teams (SDTs) and no time was created for working on the issues raised in their Personal Growth Plans (PGPs).

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) of teachers is increasingly becoming a priority in most countries throughout the world. It is widely viewed as the most effective approach to prepare teachers adequately, and to improve their instructional and intervention practices (Fraser, et al 2007). In spite of the general acceptance of CPD programmes as being essential to the improvement of education, reviews of professional development research constantly point out the ineffectiveness of most of these programmes (Cohen & Hill, 2000; Phiri, Mbozi & Kalimaposo, 2019). Furthermore, many teachers express dissatisfaction with the professional development opportunities made available to them in schools and insist that the most effective development programmes they have experienced have been self-initiated (National Research Council, 2007). There is a consensus that many CPD programmes have yet to understand professional development from a teacher's perspective. This perspective acknowledges what drives teachers to enlist in these programmes and how such programmes can make a difference to them and their classrooms.

It has been observed that CPD however well-intentioned and executed is received differently by each teacher as a result of their personal circumstances and investment in the programme. Professional development is according to Fletcher and Zuber – Skerritt (2007), a significant issue in all work places for dealing most effectively with the complexity of modern society. Unprecedented technological advancements in recent times mean that changing workplace require current knowledge to support on-going economic imperatives. Professional development is therefore a costly part of what governments, professions, companies and individuals must do to most efficiently respond to contingencies and build platforms for sustainable growth in reaction to continuous change (Kalimaposo, 2022). In education, CPD is increasingly becoming a priority in most countries throughout the world. It is widely viewed as the most effective approach to prepare teachers adequately, and improve the instructional and intervention practices (Fraser et al, 2007). Ordinarily, the CPD of teachers is one of the key factors in ensuring that education reforms, at any level are effective (Mubita et al, 2023; Kalimaposo, 2024). International evidence seems to suggest that the progress of educational reforms depends on the individual and collective capacity of teachers and its link with the school-wide promotion of the education of pupils (Stoll et al, 2006). Building the capacity to do so is thus critical, and that is what CPD aims to achieve. Various researchers on CPD concur that professional development is goal oriented and argue that it needs to be continuous and supported through a variety of techniques, and adopted to the specific needs of the students it affects (Little and Houston, 2003). Bates (2000) contends that CPD becomes effective when it is needed rather than when it is offered; this argument is based on the premise that a teacher may use the techniques learned in the programme at some point in the future. Successful CPD opportunities for teachers have positive effects on the performance and learning of students (International Institute for Education Planning, IIEP 2003). Bolam (2000) also argues that professional development is an essential part of improving school performance. Since the goal of most education reforms is to improve student learning and teacher performance, the professional development of teachers will for the foreseeable future – continue to feature prominently in larger education reforms. Teachers are at the heart of such reforms for they must execute the demands of these reforms in the classrooms. High quality CPD is inevitably a central component in nearly every modern proposal for improving education.

Teachers are expected to fulfil dual roles; teaching and engaging in CPD of teaching and learning skills (Harwood & Clarke, 2006). To do so, they must receive high quality professional development and be given time to implement what they learn through validated interventions (Deshler & Schumaker, 1993). Many professional development programmes have been proposed and all of these vary widely

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in their content and format. Most programmes, however, share a common purpose: to alter the professional practices, beliefs and understanding of school persons towards an articulated end (Guskey, 2002; Kalimaposo, 2022). CPD programmes are therefore viewed as systematic efforts to change the practices of teachers in the classroom, to change their attitudes and beliefs and to change the learning outcomes of students. Borko (2004; Kalimaposo & Muleya, 2014) provides evidence that intensive professional development programmes could help teachers to increase their knowledge and improve their teaching. Notwithstanding the general acceptance of CPD programmes as essential to the improvement of education, reviews of professional development research constantly point out the ineffectiveness of these programmes (Cohen & Hill, 2000; Phiri, Mbozi & Kalimaposo, 2018). In addition, many teachers express dissatisfaction with the professional development opportunities made available to them in schools and insist that the most effective development programmes they have experienced have been self-initiated (National Research Council, 2007). A variety of factors undoubtedly contribute to this perceived ineffectiveness; these include the fact that a majority of the programmes fail to take into account two crucial factors: what motivates teachers to engage in professional development, and what processes take place which cause a change in teachers. In other words, there is a consensus that many CPD programmes have yet to understand professional development from the teachers' perspective.

Teachers play an important role in teaching and learning process to improve student outcomes although many factors contribute to their success (Kalimaposo & Simuyaba, 2014; Mwanamwambwa et al, 2021; Kalimaposo & Kaumba, 2023). The students learning achievement depends on the readiness of teachers to do learning activities which are supported by teacher's knowledge and skills, attitude and practice. However, the quality of education depends on the quality of teacher educators is logically argued by Kalimaposo (2010) as cited in the Zambia National Education Policy, *Educating our Future*, 1996; The quality of teaching depends in large measure on the quality of teachers; the quality of teachers depends in large part upon the quality of their professional education (MoE, 1996).

They have been many calls for teacher education and professional development to be an integral part of CPD. Emphasis has been placed on the very nature of teaching profession as a continuous and lifelong career, both formal and informal. This augment is based on the fact that society is dynamic and so is the educational and school systems (Kalimaposo, 2022). The lifelong learning and career development known as Continuous Professional Development (CPD) of teachers is emerging as a key priority area internationally. CPD is the process by which teachers

(like other professionals) reflect upon their competencies, maintain them up to date and develop them further.

Globally, teacher CPD is harnessed by governments to foster teacher quality, improved student learning and enhance educational outcomes (Guskey, 2000). Enhancing teacher quality through CPD currently remains at the heart of many educational reforms based on the evidence that improving teacher quality through professional development correlates well with student learning, quality of education and in the areas of teachers' beliefs and practices (Kalimaposo & Kaumba, 2023; Melesse & Gulie, 2019).

CPD refers to those processes and activities designed to enhance the professional knowledge, skills and attitudes of educators so that they in turn improve the learning of students (Guskey, 2000). It is all forms of learning activities (both formal & informal) that teachers engage in after their initial training to improve practice to affect student learning (Abakar, 2019). CPD provides opportunities to teachers for career development thereby bringing meaningful changes in addressing equity, quality relevance, being up to date and efficiency in professional life and that of their institutions. However, effective CPD activities require sufficient duration regarding the span of time over which the activity is spread and the number of hours in the activity (Desimone, 2009; Kang, et al, 2013).

In Zambia, teacher CPD is done as school based in service training is conducted in schools through the in service training framework called "school program of in service for the term" (SPRINT) which has components such as Teacher Group Meeting (TGM); Grade Meeting At Resource Centre (GRACE) and Subject Meetings At Resource Centre (SMARC). In addition, all Head teacher and Deputy head teachers are required to undertake Head teachers In service Meeting (HIM) and School In service Meeting (SIMON) to monitor CPD activities with the view to promote teacher professionalism and enhance quality of education (MoE, 2016). According to TCZ (2021) the SPRINT activities are mandatory provided for each school routine of professional development activities. It is supported by well-established network of teacher resource centres based in schools, zone, district, provincial and national centres.

CPD may also include internal or external professional development activities such as short courses of study, seminars and conferences, work-based activities, professional network forums and self-directed informal learning that are directly relevant to one's work, career or professional development with the support of immediate supervisors (TCZ, 2021).

Despite these perceived benefits of CPD, the activities do not seem to impact the learning outcomes for teachers to transform their professional life and classroom practices. It is also centralized, fragmented and a disconnected programme which lack diversity in provision and irrelevant to the real

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problems in the classroom (Cohen & Hill, 2000; Mitchell, 2000; NEPC, 2014; Temperley et al, 2007).

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

This study used a qualitative approach to understand the experiences of teachers on CPD activities. The study used a descriptive design. This design was ideal for the study because it explores a real life, contemporary bounded system (a case) or multi bounded system (cases) overtime through a detailed in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of data collection (Creswell, 2014; Kalimaposo, 2010). In studying teachers' perspectives, it is their experiences of CPD and the meanings ascribed to those experiences that the study focused on. The sampled schools provided the context or the 'world' in which the teachers' constructions of meaning and understanding was described and interpreted. Qualitative studies provide insight into how people make sense of their experience which is not easily achieved with other methods (Raid, 2004). The study sought to explore in-depth the perspectives of teachers in Kabwe District of Central Zambia on CPD activities in schools. The study collected excerpts of the teachers' verbatim of their experiences as well as the contextual understandings of what the teachers think is effective or ineffective with regard to CPD

Research Design

A research design is a summary of the various procedures that a researcher employs to collect, analyze, interpret and includes the final presentation of the research data (Creswell & Clark, 2007; Kalimaposo, 2010). This study looked at the perceptions of teachers on CPD and analyzed the opinions of participating teachers. A descriptive qualitative study was employed in this study. This design was chosen because it allows for a multiple perspectives analysis in which the researcher considers not just the opinion and perspective of one or two participants in a situation, but also the views of the other relevant groups of actors, and the interaction between them. Thus, a descriptive qualitative design allows a greater understanding of teacher' views and experiences of CPD.

Sampling Procedures

Sampling involves selecting units of analysis such as people, groups, setting or artefacts in a manner that maximizes the researcher's ability to answer the research questions (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003; Creswell et al, 2010). In this study, purposive sampling was utilized to identify particular groups of teachers that participated in the study. Purposive sampling is defined by Creswell et al (2010: 79) as the sampling approach whereby participants are selected because of the data they hold, or represent; this data is needed for the study and thus the sampling decisions are made for the explicit purpose of obtaining the richest possible source of information to answer the research questions. The study

purposefully identified five schools in Kabwe District that participated in the study.

The target population was fifteen (15) teachers from five (5) different schools with three (3) teachers sampled from each of the five sampled schools. Accordingly, non-probability sampling techniques, namely purposive and convenience sampling were used to select teacher participants and schools respectively. The basis for choosing purposive sampling was the fact that the participants were custodians of the research's desired information since they had direct experience with the phenomenon under study (Mubita, 2017). Five (5) secondary schools in Kabwe district were selected using convenience sampling technique because of their convenient accessibility and proximity to the researcher.

Data Collection Process

The study used an in-depth face to face semi structured interview with teachers and observation to collect data on teachers' experiences on CPD. In depth interviews allowed an in depth exploration of participants' relevant experiences in more detail with richness in communication (Charmaraz, 2006). The semi structured interview equally provided an opportunity to seek further explanation and clarity to posed question leading to valuable responses (Creswell, 2013; Kalimaposo, 2010). Direct observation using the check list was used to observe how and what teachers do during the CPD meetings because it is tied directly to teacher professional development and growth. The purpose of the research was explained, and consent sought from the participants who were assured of anonymity during the research period and beyond.

Data Analysis Process

Qualitative data analysis tends to be an on-going and interactive process which implies that data collection, processing, analysis and reporting are intertwined (Creswell et al, 2010). In this study the analysis was done continuously during the data collection process as all of the conversations were recorded. Data collected were analysed thematically. Kombo and Tromp (2014) assert that in thematic analysis, major concepts or themes are identified after developing a coding system based on samples of collected data from the research objectives and questions. A cross case approach was used to develop themes in this study (Patton, 2002). Thematic analysis framework used provided the more flexible ways of identifying, analysing and interpreting consistent patterns of meaning within the data collected (Braun & Clarke, 2012). The emerging themes were later sub categorised into refined sub themes in accordance with the responses. The analysed data was presented in form of tables, graphs, and through verbatim statements. The final study findings were sent to the participants for the purpose of member checking with feedback used to revise various narratives.

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Findings

This section presents the study findings under the following themes: Forms of CPD activities, teachers' perceptions on CPD activities and impact of CPD activities on teacher professionalization and classroom practices.

Forms of CPD activities

Table 1 below shows the forms of CPD activities that teachers were involved in.

Table 1: Forms of CPD activities for teachers

<i>Form of CPD</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Formal continuing education</i>	3	20
<i>INSET activities</i>	9	60
<i>Workshop</i>	2	13.3
<i>Others (specify)</i>	1	6.7
<i>Totals</i>	15	100

Source: Field data, 2024

The study revealed that CPD activities for teachers were predominantly INSET activities 9 (60%) which were mainly subject specific, followed by formal continuing education 3 (20%) which was mainly done through distance education mode of study, workshop at 2 (13.3%) and other forms which were mainly informal learning at 1 (6.7%) as teacher 1 below reported that:

At our school CPD activities are done through INSET activities such as HIM, GRACE once in a while. These activities despite being timetabled are rare, fragmented and lack focus and consistency.

Teachers' perceptions on CPD activities

Absence of teacher consultation

Teacher consultation is the degree to which teachers are involved in framing their CPD activities. The study revealed that teachers were not consulted or involved in framing the agenda for CPD activities. The teachers expressed frustration about this practice as they had no sense of ownership for the activities as teacher 2 from school B said:

We are just told what to do every time we have CPD activities. We attend these activities as robots not knowing what to do and what to expect. Sometimes you discover that during the activity that what you are learning has no relevance to you individually and collectively.

Another teacher, teacher 4 echoed the same sentiments when she reported that:

I don't feel motivated to participate in CPD activities whose planners I don't know. Participation in such activities makes me feel like an intruder and I have no sense of ownership. The activities are not ours because if they were, we should have been consulted for us to have in input.

Infrequency CPD activities

The study revealed that CPD activities were inadequate, fragmented, disjointed and lacked consistency. CPD activities were done impulsively despite being time tabled and programmed due to many factors among them poor funding, lack of expertise and lack of implementation power by

management. This was evidenced by the report given by teacher 6 at school C who said that:

The opportunities for CPD activities are inadequate and comes once on a while. I can't remember the last time I attended an INSET. This term is almost coming to a close but there is no indication of any CPD activities.

Same sentiments were equally echoed by teacher 8 at school A who reported that:

Opportunities for CPD were rare and insufficient hence can't develop a teacher fully. CPD activities are selective and more biased towards certain subject areas such as Mathematics, Science and Technology.

Access to CPD Opportunities

Teachers had mixed feelings on the access to CPD activities. Some sections believed that access to CPD activities had discriminatory practices such as favouritism by school administrators and biasness towards certain subject areas while others believed to the contrary. This is evidenced in the reports below.

Teacher 12 from school A disclosed that:

In my view, CPDs are very important for every teacher to enhance teaching skills but my experience is that only the same teachers from this school have been attending these CPD activities especially workshops outside the school that attract money. It is quite frustrating.

Teacher 9 from School B opined that,

From my experience, we all do attend departmental CPDs but when it comes to attending CPD workshops outside the school the school administrators pick their favorite teachers to go and attend the workshop on CPD. In my view, access to attend CPD workshops is selective in my school.

Teacher 7 from school E

In my view, access to attend CPD workshops is selective in my school. Sometimes it is frustrating to note when workshop opportunities come, your subject area is always not considered.

Duration and Timing of CPD Programs

The timing for CPD activities is usually too short. The activities are loaded with a lot of materials that are compressed within the shortest possible time. It is equally difficult to find appropriate timing for CPD activities because the school time table is overloaded and so are the teachers.

Teacher 1 from school B said:

I personally have a problem with the timing and duration of CPD activities. I remember at one workshop, we were made to cover work intended for 2 weeks in 2 days. This defeated the purpose and efficiency of CPD.

Teacher 10 from school C had the same views and disclosed that:

The Ministry of Education has introduced a lot of programs which need to be implemented alongside CPD programs. Therefore, the duration and timing of CPD programs have been affected in schools.

Relevance of CPD activities on Teacher Classroom Practices

The study reviewed that there were mixed feelings with regards to the correlation between attending CPD activities and teacher classroom practices. Various reasons cited by those who saw no relevance between CPD activities as lack of motivation, high teacher pupil ratio, lack of research to inform CPD activities, lack of constant monitoring of CPD activities and lack of teacher consultation. This was opined by the report given by various teacher participants below.

Teacher 3 from school A opined that:

I feel there is relevance of what teachers learn from CPD activities and classroom practices. This is because when we return from the workshop, we share the learning experiences with colleagues so that everyone is abreast with latest development

Teacher 15 from school D had similar views

From my experience, there is little link between CPD activities and classroom practices. I do not use the knowledge I have acquired through CPD activities. I believe this is because what we do in CPD is not informed by research and that teachers are not consulted but taken as passive consumers of knowledge. CPD activities simply teach us what we know already and in most cases, they are biased toward methodology leaving content knowledge unaddressed.

Another teacher, teacher 7 from school B reported that:

From my 15 years of teaching experience, teachers generally do not practice what they learn from CPD activities as they immediately pack what they have learnt from such activities. There is nothing compelling them to do so. Most of us attend such workshops for monetary gain.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Forms of CPD activities

The study revealed that CPD activities for teachers were predominantly INSET activities that were school based while other forms such as formal continuing education mainly done through distance education mode of study and workshop outside the school environment were common. This finding resonated well with MoE (2016) which reported that Zambian teachers participate widely in continuing education workshops in and outside school as part of their CPD.

Teachers' perceptions on CPD activities

Absence of teacher consultation

Teacher consultation is the degree to which teachers are involved in framing their CPD activities. The study revealed that teachers were not consulted or involved in framing the agenda for CPD activities. The teachers expressed frustration about this practice as they have no sense of ownership for the activities. This finding contradicts Knowles (1990) who opined that for teachers as adult learners, learning becomes more meaningful if they control their own on learning with some degree of ownership. This finding suffocates the purpose of CPD as teachers are reduced to mere consumers and passive receivers of knowledge.

Infrequency CPD activities

The study revealed that CPD activities are inadequate, fragmented, disjointed and lacked consistency. CPD activities in schools appeared impulsive and selective despite being time tabled and programmed due to many factors among them poor funding, lack of expertise and lack of implementation power by management. This finding is testimony that CPD activities in Zambian schools were not meeting their mandate of enhancing the professional knowledge, skills and attitudes of educators so that they could in turn improve the learning of students (Guskey, 2000). This was because of their fragmentation and inadequacy, a sentiment earlier alluded to by NEPC (2014).

Access to CPD Opportunities

Teachers had mixed feelings on the access to CPD activities. Some sections believed that access to CPD activities had discriminatory practices such as favoritism by school administrators and biasness towards certain subject areas while others believed to the contrary. This aspect of discriminatory practice that has rocked CPD activities if not addressed has the potential to pull down opportunities to teachers for career development (Purdon, 2003) thereby fighting against the call for CPD of bringing meaningful changes in addressing equity, quality relevance, and efficiency in professional life of an individual and that of their institutions.

Duration and Timing of CPD Programs

The timing for CPD activities is usually too short. The activities are loaded with a lot of materials

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that are compressed within the shortest possible time. It is equally difficult to find appropriate timing for CPD activities because the school time table is overloaded and so are the teachers. This finding is contrary to Desimone (2009) & Kang, et al, (2013) who argued that effective CPD activities require sufficient duration regarding the span of time over which the activities are spread and the number of hours.

Relevance of CPD activities on Teacher Classroom Practices

The study reviewed that there were mixed feelings with regard to the correlation between attending CPD activities and teacher classroom practices. Some participants reported that CPD activities improved their classroom practices as they were able to blend new pedagogical knowledge in the actual teaching process. This finding is in tandem with Tang and Choi (2009) who contends that knowledge learned in CPD programmes needs to be integrated with teacher's practical knowledge and contextualised practice situations.

Various reasons cited by those who saw no relevance between CPD activities are lack of motivation, high teacher pupil ratio, lack of research to inform CPD activities, lack of constant monitoring of CPD activities and lack of teacher consultation. The finding on high teacher pupil ratio hindering relevance

of CPD on classroom practices resonates with well with Mok (2001) who said that when teachers are preoccupied with teaching overcrowded classrooms and administrative work, they are likely to reduce their intentions of participating in CPD activities and later on blend the CPD activities in the actual teaching. The finding on lack of teacher consultation hindering relevance of CPD on classroom practices was in tandem with the findings of NEPS (2014) which stated that programmes aimed towards teachers were rarely designed in the participatory matter, which would include teachers as co-creators thereby creating a gap between supply and demand, meaning that offered programs did not correspond to the needs of teachers in a classroom.

CONCLUSION

Learning is fundamental in teacher CPD; therefore, it is important to know how teachers learn in order to translate their knowledge to classroom practice. It can be concluded that teachers were fairly involved in CPD activities both as facilitators and participants. However, this became a point of frustration for some teachers who felt that participation in CPD activities was selective especially when remuneration was involved. Some teachers felt that CPD activities improved their classroom practices while others felt that CPD activities did not meet teachers at their point of need. The study concluded that CPD activities were fragmented, centralized, lacked teacher involvement as co-designers thereby failing to correspond to the need of teachers in a classroom.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study made the following recommendations:

1. The Ministry of Education and school administrators should ensure that CPD activities are decentralized and involve teachers as co-designers to promote a culture of continuous learning and foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among teachers.
2. The Ministry of Education should ensure that CPD activities are funded to facilitate procurement of material to be used during such activities and cater for teacher workshops. Participation in CPD activities should be recognized and rewarded.
3. School administrators should ensure that CPD activities are flexible and should offer diverse formats such as online, hands on activities, in-person and self-directed learning.
4. The Ministry of Education and school administrators should ensure that CPD activities are accessible and inclusive. Equal access to participate in CPD activities should be availed to all teachers regardless of their location or abilities.

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